

AMARANTH IS A PLANT OF 21ST CENTURY

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A large reserve in the decision to increase production and improve the quality of feed is the agricultural practice of new non-traditional forage plants. One such plant is the stern amaranth. Amaranth and amaranth (*Amaranthus*) belongs to the family *Amaranthaceae* (*Amaranthaceae*) and includes about 60 species, of which only a few are suitable for growing as cultivated plants. Most species in this family are the weeds and their seeds and leaves are unsuitable for use as food. Amaranth is an annual plant that reaches a height of 1 to 2.5 meters. On the premises to receive 800-1500 kg of green mass and 30-60 kilograms of seeds per hectare. Culture is very drought-resistant water requirement in the 2-2, 5 times less than that of legumes and cereals. In addition, it is virtually not affected diseases and pests. Oil obtained from the seeds and other constituents of amaranth, a plant has healing properties, is far superior to the famous Sea buckthorn oil. Amaranth refers to plants with c-4 photosynthesis, i.e. type intensively and in great quantities binds carbon dioxide from the atmosphere, which is important in terms of global warming [1].

Amaranth is a unique plant, in the sense that all its components are used to produce different products:

Green mass-to get coordinate feed additives that protein content than corn, wheat, barley, walnuts, sorghum, amaranth does invaluable food for animals. The animals quickly gaining weight;

Seeds-for the production of oils and other medicinal preparations;

the processed seeds in the baking industry. You can get a number of valuable products: flour, Bran, starch for food and beverages;

Waste oil production-raw material for the preparation of confectionary products, baby food, high-protein pastas.

When feeding the Green mass of amaranth in cows increases milk productivity, increasing the fat content of the milk. The bird is growing several times faster. The aft silage good mixture of amaranth, amaranth, corn, sunflower seeds, sorghum yields "pink" silage, which is nutritious and healthy food. The feeding of "pink" silo with amaranth increases the percentage of average daily milk yield, milk fat, gain weight and feed consumption decreases compared to the traditional diet.

Particularly high Stern virtues has herbal powder, granules or pellets, made from shredded mass of Amaranth by conventional technology. Amaranth granules have a high protein content (18-21) and carotene (240 mg/kg), well kept, easy to transport and can be used as a protein supplement (10-15%) and which increases the nutritional value of conventional feed, and, consequently, the productivity of animals, especially young animals. Products of processing of coarse of Amaranth is herbal powder (briquettes, pellets) have found use in poultry feeding practices. In the introduction to the diet of laying hens, broiler dose grass flour from amaranth in the amount of 7-15% has resulted in substantial savings in grain, not reducing the resistant capacity of laboratory animals [2].

In Russia as a result of numerous studies found that the inclusion in the diets of the cows amaranth corn silage in amaranth the number of 30-35% increase in dairy and meat productivity and reduces the cost of animal feed [3].

In Kazakhstan, with a huge deficit of protein feed and vitamins in animal husbandry, amaranth can play an important role as a high protein fodder culture. The major advantage of amaranth in front of other forage crops is its high biological productivity. Amaranth apart not only on the content of protein, fat, and calcium, phosphorus, magnesium, copper, Silicon, as well as on the total caloric value. When amaranth yields 500 centner HA green mass and seeds from 20 up to 60 c, protein output is 20 c, while barley and wheat produce 2.4 kg, rice 4, pea, soya 4.8-8 TS protein with 1 ha.

In the South and South-East of Kazakhstan seeds of amaranth to full maturity, and produces good yields and plant seeds and green mass. In the northern regions of the country using the medium for planting and early varieties you can get high-yielding vitamin silage. Multiple cutting culture. Depending on the region of cultivation you can mow down 2-3 times, receiving the high-protein fodder and silage. High yields at normal planting 1.5 kg seeds per 1 hectare, suggest that amaranth could become one of the major cultures of human life. The Food Commission has recognized 21 century culture amaranth. Using modern methods of plant breeding, created new varieties of amaranth in the United States, Argentina, Mexico, China, Russia and Ukraine [4, 5, 6]. In China, the amaranth is cultivated on an area of more than 8000ga

In the Republic of Kazakhstan amaranth can be sown in the northern and Eastern regions, in particular in Kostanai and East Kazakhstan regions. According to the State Register of plant varieties in the Republic of Kazakhstan in the Republic are officially allowed to use only one variety of Amaranth Atlanta (Ukrainian Research Institute of forages) in three regions (Almaty, East-Kazakhstan, South-Kazakhstan) from 1995 onwards [7].

Among the varieties with promising use in the northern regions of Kazakhstan are sort of the Cherginsky, which is SibNIIHoze (Omsk) in 1995, and included in the State register on the Western Siberian region of Russia, the sort of fodder and grain supplies, is promising for cultivation for medicinal purposes [8]. There are varieties of amaranth, giving up to 50 kilograms of seeds per hectare. Average maize yields-24-23, rice, wheat-15.6 centners per hectare. As for the biomass, the culture of the fantastic: without watering amaranth can provide up to 2 thousand quintals, and irrigated hectare-up to 4 000 [9, 10, 11].

Currently, Kazakhstan is just 6-7 centners of fodder units of a conditional that the 2.5 times lower than the zoo technical standards. Share of fodder crops in the rotation is only 11%, whereas the recommended proportion should be 30%. The main sources of food become difficult natural hay meadows. The cultivation of amaranth in regions with arid climate are producing positive results compared to other cultures. There are examples where a fairly good harvest amaranth in drought conditions. So, in Pavlovsk near Voronezh oblast received the yield of green mass of more than 300 kg/ha in the phase of beginning of buttonhole (corn on the adjacent field gave less harvest almost in 2 times). The pilot plots using ammonium nitrate fertilizer was obtained yields of varieties of "Gigant" 650 c/HA green mass yields of grain of the same class 34 centners/hectare. In the Èrtel district of Voronezh region was received biological yields about 2 t/ha of grain amaranth variety Voronezh [12].

The main disadvantages are the amaranth [13]:-Shattering seeds and clogging the fields. In Northern Kazakhstan, given the large debris fields amaranth its ability to self seeding it is not recommended to put high-quality crops.

With the escalation of the amaranth forms a high and strong stems that become rough. When feeding amaranth gross and thick stalks are reluctant to eat the animals. Also badly eaten by animals raceme brush of amaranth (love-lies-bleeding and other);

Introduction of amaranth in agricultural production is impeded by the malicious weed, prevailing among the population. Well known in the world of widespread weed plant amaranth also represents the family of Amaranth. Therefore, the choice of variety for introductions require a precautionary approach.

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